

The **PlastChemTox evidence map (EM)** addresses the following question:

Which types of toxicities/bioactivities have been measured for chemical mixtures released from which plastic polymers or products, and mixtures from which plastic polymers or products were found to exhibit which types of toxicities/bioactivities?

We will not carry out a fully systematic evidence map (SEM) due to the shortage of time and resources (e.g., we will not publish a SEM protocol) but will perform a semi-systematic evidence map (EM) instead. We will ensure transparent recording of our literature searches, study screening and data extraction procedures at all times. For this, we will use the free online tool CADIMA¹ at the literature search and selection stages for study handling and documentation purposes (Kohl et al. 2018), and the custom-built SciExtract tool at the data extraction stage (Geueke et al. 2022). We performed a semi-systematic literature search on April 5th, 2023. The results were filtered for research articles, that is, reviews, abstracts, editorial material etc. were excluded. After removal of duplicates in CADIMA, this set contains 5854 papers. Title/abstract screening and full-text screening will be performed in CADIMA following the **general considerations** and **PI/EO criteria** as outlined below.

General considerations and remarks

- If all three criteria used at the title/abstract screening stage are categorized as “yes” or “unclear”, the study will move to the full text screening
- If one or more criteria used at the title/abstract screening stage are categorized as “no”, the study will be excluded
- We aim to include primary research studies and exclude the following literature types: reviews, abstracts, dissertations etc.; therefore, if you see a clear indication that a paper is one of these types, choose the “no” category at the top to exclude it directly (this will mark all three criteria as “no”)
- If a study is clearly irrelevant on the first glance, you should also select the “no” at the top; this can be done like this even if one of the criteria would have been met (and therefore should have been marked as “yes” instead of “no”); we chose to allow such handling in order to save time, as it is a faster way to exclude the study compared to always having to provide a differentiated marking for each criterion
- If you have had to spend some minutes evaluating the abstract and then identified a specific criterion which led to the exclusion in the end, you should categorize this criterion as “no” while categorizing other criteria (that you found to be met) as “yes”; this will allow for some traceability and highlighting of criteria that frequently led to study exclusion
- If you are not completely certain whether a study is meeting a particular criterion or criteria, and therefore cannot categorize it/them as “yes”, but you do see indications in the title/abstract that it might be relevant, then you should choose the “unclear” category for these particular criterion/criteria

¹ www.cadima.info

- The studies categorized as “unclear” for one or more criteria after the title/abstract screening stage will undergo a targeted full-text screening, where we will aim to evaluate their relevance and inclusion or exclusion for the subsequent data extraction
- The studies categorized as “yes” for all three criteria will not be subjected to full-text screening but will be evaluated directly during the data extraction stage, where exclusion of studies that turn out to be irrelevant/ineligible will still be made possible, provided the reasons for exclusion are transparently documented; we chose this strategy in order to save time, because subjecting all studies categorized as “yes” in all three criteria to a full-text screening before the data extract stage would have led to us having to handle most of the papers twice (i.e., during the full-text screening and during the data extraction stage)

PI/EO criteria

P – Population

Plastic materials or products, including pre-production pellets as well as virgin, recycled, and compounded materials.

Include:

- Studies on elastomers (e.g., rubber), inorganic polymers (e.g., silicones), polymeric coatings and paints (e.g., acrylic) and products made out of them (rationale: these are synthetic polymers similar to plastics, with similar exposure pathways and which can often contain mixtures of unknown substances as well; we acknowledge though that we have not made a comprehensive search for these materials, so the inclusion of any studies appearing in our set is being done only for comparative purposes)
- Studies on polymeric dental fillings (rationale: high relevance for human exposure)

Exclude:

- Studies with plastics collected in the environment, including both microplastics and larger plastic debris (rationale: these samples are likely to also contain chemicals adsorbed from the environment, which are out of scope in this evidence map)
- Studies with water-soluble polymers (rationale: toxicity originates from dissolved polymer, not a release of other chemicals)
- Studies with experimental materials that were produced by the authors themselves for their specific study (rationale: market use of such materials is often unclear)
- Studies of single compounds (e.g., alternatives for replacement of specific plastic additives) or studies with experimental materials supplemented with a specific chemical that were produced by the authors for their specific study (rationale: we focus on chemical mixtures in the leachates and not on any individual intentionally added substance; market use of such materials is often unclear)

- Studies with materials intended for use in the active or intelligent packaging (rationale: these materials are produced for the purpose of facilitated intentional release of chemicals, and hence the biotests are usually applied to evaluate the intended effects of intentionally released chemical(s), such as antimicrobial or antifungal activity, but not any other types of effects which could be induced by any co-released chemicals or mixtures; focus is usually on individual substances or substance mixtures such as essential oils; market use of such materials is often unclear)

I – Intervention / E – Exposure

Release of chemical mixtures from plastic materials or products in any type of medium, that is, leachates, migrates, extracts etc. of chemicals in aqueous, solid, or gaseous media.

Include:

- Studies that investigate degradation products of plastic materials or products, for instance from microbial or photooxidative degradation (rationale: we consider this to be a special type of “leaching”)
- Note, especially with regard to the nano- and microplastics toxicity studies: sometimes the authors do mention the impact of leaching chemicals in the abstract, but it is not clear from the abstract whether a proper leaching study was actually designed (as opposed to testing both particles and leaching chemicals together); in this case the paper should be categorized as “unclear”, which marks it for targeted evaluation in the full-text screening phase

Exclude:

- Nano- and microplastics toxicity studies and studies with any other particulate material (e.g., engineered nanomaterials) where study design does not seem to permit distinguishing between physical (particle) and chemical toxicity, and where the impact of leaching chemicals is not mentioned in the abstract (rationale: this indicates that a particular study did not focus on the toxicity of chemical leachates from plastic particles)
- Studies on contaminated foodstuff or extracted foodstuff previously in contact with plastic materials or products (rationale: complex matrix and uncertainty regarding the source of extracted chemicals, as they could originate from sources other than packaging)
- Studies on bottled or packaged water UNLESS there was a temporal design (i.e., time-course experiment) demonstrating that chemicals originate from the bottle/plastic packaging

O – Outcome

Toxicity testing of chemical mixtures released by plastic materials or products in any type of bioassay, regardless of the results obtained in that bioassay.

Include:

- Tests that assess not only an explicitly defined toxicity (e.g., cytotoxicity) but also any types of bioactivities that could lead to organism toxicity (e.g., endocrine activity)
- Both *in vitro* and *in vivo* bioassays based on any organism (i.e., both the unicellular and multicellular plants and animals as well as bacteria and other microbes are included)
- Any test setup (e.g., both acute and chronic exposures, single and multiple dosing etc.)
- Studies that performed some chemical analyses for individual chemicals possibly contained in the tested chemical mixtures AND additionally tested the whole mixture (not individual chemicals!) in any type of a bioassay

Exclude:

- Studies that conducted chemical analyses only (i.e., chemical mixtures obtained from plastic materials or products were subjected only to chemical analyses but were not tested in any type of a bioassay)
- Studies that tested only individual/single chemicals

Note: Our statement does not include part C (**C – Comparison**). This is because, although we do intend to compare between different plastic polymers/products causing different types of bioactivities, this aim does not influence the initial collection and selection of literature sources – a process that is hence defined by the PI/EO parameters only.

References

Kohl, C.; McIntosh, E. J.; Unger, S.; Haddaway, N. R.; Kecke, S.; Schiemann, J.; Wilhelm, R. (2018): Online tools supporting the conduct and reporting of systematic reviews and systematic maps: a case study on CADIMA and review of existing tools. *Environmental Evidence*. 7, 8. DOI: [10.1186/s13750-018-0115-5](https://doi.org/10.1186/s13750-018-0115-5)

Geueke, B.; Groh, K.J.; Maffini, M.V.; Martin, O.V.; Boucher, J.M.; Chiang, Y.-T.; Gwosdz, F.; Jieh, P.; Kassotis, C.D.; Lanska, P.; Myers, J.P.; Odermatt, A.; Parkinson, L.V.; Schreier, V.N.; Srebny, V.; Zimmermann, L.; Scheringer, M.; Muncke, J. (2022): Systematic evidence on migrating and extractable food contact chemicals: Most chemicals detected in food contact materials are not listed for use. *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition*. 1-11. DOI: [10.1080/10408398.2022.2067828](https://doi.org/10.1080/10408398.2022.2067828)